

DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF MAJORITY LOGIC BASED APPROXIMATE ADDERS AND MULTIPLIERS

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ABSTRACT: Many studies have focused on approximate computer arithmetic circuits that use CMOS technology. Proposals have been made for approximation addition, multiplication, and division algorithms in both fixed-point and floating-point formats. Appropriate computing has arisen as a low power design technique for arithmetic circuits and allows error tolerance in the computational process; it is a new paradigm in nano size technology. The three-input majority voter, the fundamental building block of majority logic (ML), has found widespread use in digital circuit design and has potential applications in other new technologies. Here, we provide a majority-logic-based solution for a one-bit approximation complete adder. We also study and propose multi-bit approximation full adders and show how these designs might be used to quantum-dot cellular automata (QCA). Hardware measures, such as area and delay, and error metrics are used to assess the designs. Results show that the ideal designs outperform competing circuits described in the technical literature. One of the most important parts of signal processing and transmission are finite impulse response filters. The design of a FIR filter includes a delay unit, an adder, and multipliers. The FIR filter relies heavily on the adder and multiplier unit for its performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

These days, the general population is very interested in nanotechnology. Researchers are looking for new technologies since the existing silicon transistor technology has a lot of drawbacks, such a lot of power consumption and a hard time reducing feature sizes. Among the potential future solutions, quantum-dot cellular

automata (QCA) stands out. There have been advancements in experimental devices for semiconductor, molecular, and magnetic techniques since its first introduction in 1993. Boolean logic functions may be implemented using quantum dot cellular automata, which are arrays of connected quantum dots. Because the dots are so tiny in QCA, the connecting is simplified, and the area delay product is minimal. This allows for very high packing densities. An early method for quantizing a cellular automaton model was proposed by Richard Feynman in 1982. David Deutsch introduced a more structured evolution of the topic in 1985. The phrase "quantum cellular automata" was later used by Gerhard Grössing and Anton Zeilinger to describe a model they proposed in 1988. However, their model differed greatly from Deutsch's ideas and has therefore not been much used as a computational model. John Watrous presented the first rigorous model of quantum cellular automata that was extensively studied. Wim van Dam, Christoph Dürr, Huong Lê Thanh, Miklos Santha, Jozef Gruska, and Pablo Arrighi all contributed to expanding upon this paradigm. But it turned out that this was an overly broad definition in the sense that

that superluminal signalling is possible in some cases of it. The models created by Benjamin Schumacher and Reinhard Werner, Carlos Pérez-Delgado and Donny Cheung, Pablo Arrighi, Vincent Nesme, and Reinhard Werner are all part of a second wave of models. There is no such locality problem with these closely linked things. All things considered, it seems like they all see quantum cellular automata as essentially a huge quantum circuit that cycles through all possible states indefinitely. A quantum cellular automaton, or QCA, is a model of quantum computing that mimics the classical cellular

automata that von Neumann first proposed. The term might also be used to describe quantum dot cellular automata, a way whereby "classical" cellular automata could be physically implemented by taking use of quantum mechanical processes. The very low power consumption and incredibly tiny feature size (on the molecular or even atomic scale) of QCA have made it a prominent contender for the replacement of CMOS technology, which has garnered a lot of interest.

One promising new approach for creating ultra-dense, low-power, high-performance digital circuits is the quantum-dot cellular automaton, or QCA [1]. That is why there has been a flurry of activity in recent years devoted to improving QCA logic circuit design. The fundamental operation of any digital system, binary addition [11]-[16], is the primary focus of arithmetic circuits [2]-[16]. Naturally, the new design environment has as its starting point the architectures often used in conventional CMOS systems. In [11], conditional sum adders, ripple-carry (RCA), and carry look-ahead (CLA) were introduced. Figure 12 shows a carry-flow adder (CFA), which was primarily an improved RCA in which detrimental wires effects were mitigated. Parallel-prefix architectures, including Brent-Kung (BKA), Kogge-Stone, Ladner-Fischer, and Han-Carlson adders were analyzed and implemented in QCA in [13] and [14]. Recently, more efficient designs were proposed in [15] for the CLA and the BKA, and in [16] for the CLA and the CFA.

2. APPROXIMATE HYBRID ADDER

A digital circuit that adds numbers is called an adder or a summer in the electronics field. In addition to their use in the arithmetic logic unit(s), adders find other applications in various processors, such as those that compute addresses, table indices, and related tasks. Most adders work with binary numbers, but they may be built for other representations as well, including decimal, excess-3, and binary-coded integers. It is easy to convert an adder into an adder subtractor or when negative values are represented by two's or ones' complement. For other representations of signed numbers, a more complex adder is necessary. A number of adder designs in QCA have been suggested, and a performance comparison has been enhanced; adders are essential circuits for the majority of digital systems. Reducing the area and minimising the carry propagation latency are two factors that contribute to improved adder performance.

The suggested adder architecture still works in the RCA way, but it outperforms all state-of-the-art rivals in terms of

computational latency and achieves the lowest area-delay product (ADP). One definition of a quantum tunnelling antenna (QCA) is a nanostructure with a fundamental cell that consists of a square with four quantum dots charged with two free electrons that may tunnel through the dots [1]. Coulombic repulsion ensures that the two electrons will always occupy opposing corners. The

locations of the electrons in the cell (also named polarizations P) determine two possible stable states that can be associated to the binary states 1 and 0.

Although adjacent cells interact through electrostatic forces and tend to align their polarizations, QCA cells do not have intrinsic data flow directionality. To achieve controllable data directions, the cells within a QCA design are partitioned into the so-called clock zones that are progressively associated to four clock signals, each phase shifted by 90° . This clock scheme, named the zone clocking scheme, makes the QCA designs intrinsically pipelined, as each clock zone behaves like a D-latch [8]. QCA cells are used for both logic structures and interconnections that can exploit either the coplanar cross or the bridge technique [1], [2], [5], [17], [18]. The fundamental logic gates inherently available within the QCA technology are the inverter and the MG. Given three inputs a , b , and c , the MG performs the logic function reported in (1) provided that all input cells are associated to the same clock signal clk_x (with x ranging from 0 to 3), whereas the remaining cells of the MG are associated to the clock signal clk_{x+1} operands by cascading n full-adders (FAs). Even though these addition circuits use different topologies of the generic FA, they have a carry-in to carry-out path consisting of one MG, and a carry-in to sum bit path containing two MGs plus one inverter. As a consequence, the worst case computational paths of the n -bit RCA and the n -bit CFA consist of $(n+2)$ MGs and one inverter.

$$M(abc) = a \cdot b + a \cdot c + b \cdot c \quad (1)$$

A CLA architecture formed by 4-bit slices was also presented in [11]. In particular, the auxiliary propagate and generate signals, namely $pi = ai + bi$ and $gi = ai \cdot bi$, are computed for each bit of the operands and then they are grouped four by four. Such a

A computational route consisting of seven cascaded MGs and one inverter makes up the planned n-bit CLA. In order to calculate grouped propagate and grouped produce signals, four cascaded MGs are

$$C_{out} = AB + BC + AC = M(A, B, C)$$

inserted into the computational route, which can be readily proved by looking at the fact that, given the propagate and generate signals, only one MG is needed. There is an additional need of one level of CLA logic for every factor of four in the operands word-length in order to calculate the carry signals. As a result, the computational route requires $\log_4 n$ layers of CLA logic, with each level contributing four cascaded MGs, in order to handle n-bit addends. The last step, sum bit calculation, adds one inverter and two more cascaded MGs. More efficient fundamental CLA logic structures are used by the parallel-prefix BKA as shown in [13]. The BKA's ability to achieve decreased computational latency is its key benefit over the adders that were previously disclosed. In its worst-case computational route, processing n-bit operands involves four $4 \times \log_2 n - 3$ cascaded MGs and a single inverter. In addition to the level needed for propagation computation and signal generation, the prefix tree has two stages that are $2 \times \log_2 n$. The logic equations given in [13] make it easy to verify that the computational route takes one MG from the first tree stage, one from the final tree stage, and two cascaded MGs from each of the intermediate levels. Two more cascaded MGs and an inverter are then integrated to compute the sum bits. The HYBA, a hybrid adder described in [14], combines the RCA with a parallel prefix adder, with the primary goal of minimising latency and area. One inverter, two cascaded MGs, and $2 \times \log_2 n$ make up the worst computational route in this architecture when dealing with n-bit operands. By using the approach suggested in [15], the CLA's worst-case scenario is reduced to $4 \times \log_4 n + 2 \times$

MGs and an inverter totaling $\log_4 n - 1$. The BKA may likewise be designed using the aforementioned method. While keeping the same computational approach, the total area is lowered in comparison to [13]. The computational pathways of the CLA are reduced to $7 + 2 \times \log_2(n/8)$ MGs and one inverter, and of the CFA to $(n/2) + 3$ MGs and one inverter, respectively, by using the decomposition approach shown in [16].

EXISTING SYSTEM

Fig. 1 shows a one-bit accurate full adder based on ML; it consists of 3 majority gates and 2 inverters. The inputs to the one-bit adder are given by A, B, C while S and Cout are the outputs. The outputs Cout and S are expressed as follows:

$$S = A \oplus B \oplus C = M(\overline{C_{out}}, M(A, B, \overline{C}), C)$$

Fig. 1. One-bit accurate full adder: Labrado et al have proposed a one-bit approximate fulladder (AFA1), whose schematic and layout are shown in Fig. 2. AFA1 produces the output S as the complement of Cout but introduces 2 errors (among the 8 input combinations) when computing the output S, (as shown in Table I). The circled entries in the truth table denote the instances in which

the outputs of the approximate full adder differ from the accurate full adder. The equations for the carry out and the sum are as follows:

3

$$S = \overline{C_{out}}$$

4

$$C_{out} = M(A, B, C)$$

Fig. 2. One-bit approximate full adder:

Inputs			Accurate		AFA1[3]		AFA2	
A	B	C	C_{out}	S	C_{out}	S	C_{out}	S
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1
0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1
1	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0
1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

TABLE I. ONE-BIT APPROXIMATE FULL ADDER TRUHTTABLE

3. PROPOSED ONE-BIT APPROXIMATE FULL ADDER

Inspired, we propose a new one-bit approximate full adder, namely, AFA2. Consider the truth table in Table I, C_{out} is nearly the same as C except in two of the 8 input combinations. Therefore, as in Eq. (5), C can be approximately considered as C_{out} to save a majority gate compared with the one-bit accurate full adder when computing the carry out of a one-bit full adder. Based on Eq. (9), the inexact output C_{out} is substituted into Eq. (3) to find the approximate output S as follows:

5

$$C_{out} = C$$

Fig. 3. Proposed one-bit approximate fulladder

5 PROPOSED TWO-BIT APPROXIMATE ADDERS

The inputs to the two-bit adder are given by $A = a_1a_0$, $B = b_1b_0$, C_0 , while $S = s_1s_0$, and C_{out} are the outputs. By cascading two one-bit approximate full adders (AFA1 and AFA2), four different combinations are possible for the two-bit approximate full adder; they are shown in Fig.4.4. AFA1 cascaded with AFA1 results in the two-bit AFA11 design. Similarly, AFA2 cascaded with AFA2 results in AFA22 design. AFA12 consists of AFA1 and AFA2, in which AFA1 is used to compute the LSB; the opposite is applicable to AFA21.

Fig. 4. Schematics of proposed 2-bit approximate full adders.

6. PROPOSED FOUR-BIT APPROXIMATE ADDERS

Consider a four-bit adder with inputs given

Signs

show better

overall performance than the other

Two schemes. These four combinations are shown in Fig 4.5

by $A = a_3a_2a_1a_0$, $B = b_3b_2b_1b_0$, C_0 and outputs given by $S = s_3s_2s_1s_0$, C_{out} . Similar to the two-bit approximate full adder, we can design a four-bit approximate full adder by cascading two two-bit approximate full adders. AFA12 and AFA21 are selected

Fig. 5. Schematics of proposed 4-bit approximate full adders:

7. PROPOSED EIGHT-BIT APPROXIMATE ADDERS

Consider an eight-bit adder with inputs, $A = a_7a_6a_5a_4a_3a_2a_1a_0$, $B = b_7b_6b_5b_4b_3b_2b_1b_0$, C_0 and outputs, $S = s_7s_6s_5s_4s_3s_2s_1s_0$, C_{out} . We have designed eight-bit approximate adders by cascading two four-bit approximate adders by using AFA1212 and AFA2121, as they show better overall performance than the other two designs.

Fig. 6. Schematics of proposed 8-bit approximate full adders

8 MLACS BASED ON 1-BIT MLAFAS

MLACs based on 1-bit MLAFAs In 4:2 compressors, there are two full adders, referred to as models 1 and 2 from upside to downside (as defined in [16]). 1-bit MLAFAs are used to replace the exact versions. Six different designs are

investigated by employing through various combinations of MLAFA1 and MLAFA2 (Fig. 4.7). For MLAC21, module 1 utilizes MLAFA2 while the other uses MLAFA1. There are two schemes when MLAFA2 is employed as module 2. So, MLAC22-1 and MLAC12-1 employ the input of the compressor as Carry and use its negation to calculate Sum, while MLAC22-2 and MLAC12-2 employ the output of module 1 as Carry.

Fig. 7. Schematic diagrams of proposed approximate 4:2 compressor: (a) MLAC11 (MLAC2 [15]), (b) MLAC22-1, (c) MLAC22-2, (d) MLAC12- 1, (e) MLAC12- 2, and (f) MLAC21

During compression, this design uses the distribution of the PPs for compression to shorten the length of the critical path. By using a pipeline, an efficient design of the PPR circuitry is studied for 4 _ 4 and 8 _ 8 MLAM designs with different number of added complement bits for exact and approximate compression, respectively, to obtain only 2 rows (or a carry in the lowest order). In particular for an 8 _ 8 MLAM design in addition to the approach mentioned above, there is yet another structure in which 4_4 MLAMs are used to design 8 _ 8 MLAMs.

9 4_4 MLAMS

A. Exact Compression (EC)

1-bit adders are used for PP compression. Four different compression schemes are presented depending on the number of complement bits (which require one stage of compression as shown in Fig. 13). The PPs within the solid line represent an arithmetic

unit. The number of complement bits does not affect the critical path. Independently of the selection of the complement bits, a 4-bit adder is required to compute the final result. The difference between these four schemes is the number of 1-bit adders used for compression.

B. Approximate Compression (AC)

To further reduce hardware and delay, the proposed MLAFAs and compressors can be utilized in the reduction circuitry. In Fig. 14(a) and Fig. 14(c)-(e), the exact adders can be changed to approximate adders for approximate compression; the PPs circled by dotted lines indicate the approximate arithmetic units.

Fig.8. Approximate PPR circuitry design for 4 _ 4 MLAMs: (a) MLAMAC1 (p=1), (b) MLAM-AC2 (p=1), (c) MLAM-AC (p=2), (d) MLAM-AC2 (p=3), (e) MLAM-AC1 (p=4), and (f) MLAM-AC2 (p=4).

The proposed compressors are employed when p is 1; an approximate compressor whose inputs come from the output of 1-bit MLAFA, is shown in Fig. 14(b). When considering the delay, the PPs on the right side of the middle line are better compressed by the arithmetic circuits (they have the same delay as the left compression circuits). Two 1-bit EFAs (rather than a 2-bit MLAFA) are selected to better control the errors; if an approximate compressor with 2 outputs is employed, a 3-bit half adder is required

for the final result. Otherwise, a 3-bit full adder is required when using an approximate compressor with 3 outputs.

However when p increases, the errors increase; consequently, a further approximation is proposed for larger values of p . When p is 4, Fig. 4.8(f) shows another method for compression (i.e. to replace one of the 1-bit MLAFAs of lower weight with a 2-bit MLAFA).

10 8 _ 8 MLAMS USING 4 _ 4 MLAMS

8 _ 8 MLAMs can be designed using 4 _ 4 MLAMs as a module, so generating 4 rows of PPs. Independently of the selection of the complement bits and PPR circuitry, 4 _ 4 MLAMs generate an 8-bit result. Therefore, the PPs can be compressed by utilizing eight 1-bit full adders to generate 2 lines requiring an additional 11-bit full adder. To further reduce the hardware, these eight 1-bit full adders can be replaced by approximate adders too. Four 4 _ 4 MLAMs are used so 4

_ 4 combinations (based on the number of complement bits) are possible; however, as in Section 4.2, complement bits of the MSBs can be omitted or reserved for the LSBs in this scheme, as reduction of hardware is not the primary objective. Only the cases of using the same type of 4 _ 4 MLAM with approximate compression are presented because they have better performance according to the previous discussion; so 4_4 MLAM-AC2 ($p=1$) using MLAC22-2 and 4_4 MLAMAC2 ($p=4$) are selected.

11 RESULTS

CONCLUSION

There is a little loss in accuracy but significant savings in area, time, and gate count with the one-bit and multi-bit approximation full adders that the project suggests. The mathematical viewpoint has been used in this study to approach the design and implementation of FIR filters. Delay time has been minimised by using the adder and multiplier. To make multiplication faster, Booth encoding was used. Using the signed-digit number system, the authors created, modelled, and evaluated a fast FIR filter.

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